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The prediction of knowledge Management through Organizational Culture in sports organizations

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Abstract

Today, Organizational culture has an important role in implementation of Knowledge management in any organization. Therefore, the purpose of this research was to predict of knowledge management through organizational culture in sports organizations.

The Statistical popularly was all managers of National Olympic committee, National Paralympics committee, National Olympic Academy, and Sport Federations (N=225). Base on Morgan table, ۱۲۴ people were selected to this research with random stratified sampling method.

Probst & et al. (2000) knowledge management questionnaire and Edwin (2006) organizational culture questionnaire was used to collect data. Data analysis was performed by the Bivariate and multivariate regression. The results of present study showed there was significant relationship between knowledge management and organizational culture ($p < 0.05$). Also, organizational flexibility, organizational compatibility and organizational participation had significant relationship with Knowledge management. But, organizational mission hadn't significant relationship with knowledge management ($p > 0.05$).

With regard to these results, notice to organizational culture in work place by sport managers can as an effective factor for enhancement of knowledge management.

Key Words: organizational flexibility, organizational compatibility, organizational participation

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